

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 6, No. 8; August 28, 2000

Dear Readers:

Here is another issue of J.UCS that I am sure you will enjoy. With this issue we have now reached almost 900 pages: this year's volume will be one of the largest ever! However, all indications are that next year we will still have more contributions: thus, the original aim that J.UCS will be a broad and large journal covering all areas of computer science in electronic form, with printed archival versions, is now taking more concrete shape.

We are working on the backlog of printed volumes: they will become rapidly available now for those who want them for archival purposes, and we are working on new ways of subscribing to J.UCS: for a small fee readers will have access to a large but limited number of papers in all past and future issues of J.UCS. The reason for this is the broad spectrum of J.UCS - in this way, readers who are only interested in a particular area will not need a full subscription to J.UCS, yet will have access to all papers of interest.

If you have comments on this (additional) subscription model, please do let me know!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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